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10.5281/zenodo.20546545

The Ritual of Sewing a Frog's Mouth Shut in the Folk Magical Tradition of the Hetmanate and Its Cultural Parallels

ABSTRACT

This article examines the folk ritual of sewing shut a live frog's mouth within the broader context of binding magic practices. Drawing upon judicial and investigative archival records from the Hetmanate period (18th-century Ukraine), the study analyzes the ritual's structure, sequence of actions, and place within traditional systems of magical belief.

To assess the reliability of the historical evidence, a comparative approach is employed, juxtaposing Ukrainian materials with historical and contemporary examples of analogous rituals documented in Latin America, the Caribbean, and Western Europe.

The study demonstrates that this ritual belonged to the sphere of sympathetic magic and functioned as a means of symbolic influence upon social relations, particularly in legal and judicial and political contexts. The evidence suggests that the practice was not merely a literary or judicial construct but formed part of the lived folk culture of the Hetmanate. The article also identifies directions for further cross-cultural research into the historical distribution and cultural significance of this ritual phenomenon.

Keywords: Hetmanate, folk magic, witchcraft, binding magic, sympathetic magic, Tripillia, frog, judicial magic.

Research on the folk traditions of Ukraine in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries has generally focused on such ethnographic domains as folk songs, festive customs, traditional dress, and related aspects of cultural life. By contrast, the role and nature of sacred beliefs, particularly those that were socially taboo, including traditions associated with witchcraft and folk magic, remain comparatively understudied.

This situation can be explained by two factors. First, only a limited body of relevant sources has been introduced into scholarly circulation. Second, during the Soviet period, the study of such phenomena was discouraged, while evidence relating to magical beliefs and practices was often dismissed as mere “survivals” of a pre-modern worldview.

The study of specific ritual actions as tangible expressions of folk belief systems therefore provides an opportunity to gain insight into the less visible dimensions of social life in the early modern and modern periods.

Particular importance should be attached to primary sources and archival documents, since they preserve the historical context and details of ritual practices that may be lost in later interpretations.

At the same time, the researcher must remain aware of the nature of the surviving documentary evidence. Since acts associated with witchcraft were subject to legal prosecution, it would be unreasonable to expect the principal participants—whether the alleged practitioner, accomplices, or clients—to provide testimony that would directly incriminate themselves.

For scholars interested primarily in ritual practices, such testimonies present a significant interpretative challenge. A central question is how to distinguish descriptions of rituals that may have actually existed from fabrications, misunderstandings, or self-justifications offered by the participants themselves.

In this regard, a comparative approach is particularly valuable, as it allows the analysis of independent cases involving similar ritual actions. However, in the Ukrainian context, surviving witchcraft cases preserved in archives and published sources are relatively rare. Consequently, the discovery of comparable examples is often a matter of considerable fortune.

For this reason, it becomes necessary to compare Ukrainian evidence with analogous practices documented in other ethnocultural settings. Yet a comparison based exclusively on historical sources creates a similar problem: did such rituals actually exist in practice, or were they merely textual constructions?

Particularly valuable in this respect are traditions in which comparable rituals continue to exist today. In such cases, researchers can draw not only upon verbal accounts but also upon photographs, material evidence, and eyewitness testimony. By examining the morphological characteristics of ritual objects and the accounts of contemporary observers, it becomes possible to assess the practical reality of particular ritual actions, including those documented in historical sources.

The ritual examined in this study is especially noteworthy because it leaves material traces in the form of injured animals, requires specific ritual implements such as thread and needles, and involves practical preparations, including the capture and transport of amphibians.

As will be shown below, these circumstances significantly broaden the circle of individuals involved in the ritual process. Indeed, even the procurement of silk thread of a particular colour became an important element in the investigation and served as evidence that the alleged practitioner had prepared for the ritual in advance.

A typical example of the ritual of sewing shut a frog's mouth in Ukraine can be found in a case heard by the Chernihiv Regimental Court in 1733 (1). The case describes an attempt to influence an official decision through magical means. A Cossack woman acting as a ritual practitioner, assisted by her clients, caught a frog, sewed its mouth shut with green thread, and recited the following incantation:

“It is not the frog's mouth that we sew shut, but the mouths of the Chernihiv colonel, the judges, and all the regimental officers, from the highest to the lowest.”

This case has come down to us through a secondary account. To better understand the ritual and its context, it is therefore necessary to turn directly to archival evidence.

A more detailed example is found in a witchcraft case involving a tavern keeper from the town of Trypillia in 1760 (2). In a previous study (3), certain aspects of the cemetery rituals described in this case were examined. Here, attention will be focused on the frog ritual itself.

The records describe two instances of this type of magical practice. The first was recounted by an accomplice who reported the alleged practitioner to the authorities. The second derives from the testimony of the accused woman herself. She denied the accusation and claimed that the information contained in the denunciation referred to another incident involving a fellow tavern keeper from a different locality who had been imprisoned and had resorted to magical practices in an attempt to secure her release.

Let us begin with the latter case. According to the testimony, a tavern keeper from Pereiaslav had been imprisoned because of debt. While in custody, she persuaded a guard to catch a frog at dawn and bring it to her cell. She then sewed the animal's mouth shut with black silk thread. Shortly thereafter, she was released from prison.

Figure 1. Graphic reconstruction of a ritual practitioner sewing shut a frog's mouth in prison¹

Even more detailed information can be derived from the ritual allegedly performed by the accused woman herself in Trypillia. According to the testimony, the ritual required the capture of a frog at dawn, the sewing shut of its mouth with black silk thread, and its subsequent placement beneath an earthenware pot while the practitioner listened to what it "said." The accused emphasized that she had successfully performed the ritual before and that, as a result, "the nobles had treated her kindly."

This suggests that the ritual was intended to influence social hierarchies and interpersonal relations, facilitating favourable outcomes in everyday disputes, business affairs, and other situations in which decisions depended upon the goodwill of socially superior individuals.

The ritual of "closing the mouth" and the associated practices were apparently regarded as unusual even by those familiar with magical activities. The accused woman's assistant, who had previously accompanied her in the performance of cemetery rituals, refused to participate. The practitioner was therefore willing to compromise, asking only that the frog be brought to her, while she would carry out the remainder of the ritual herself.

The case was investigated in considerable detail. Statements were collected from numerous local residents and neighbours. Particular attention was devoted to the purchase of black silk thread, including questions concerning who had bought it, from whom, and when. As silk thread of this kind was a relatively scarce commodity, its acquisition attracted the attention of the investigators. Consequently, the evidence points not merely to the imagination of a single individual but to a broader layer of lived folk beliefs and ritual practices embedded within the local community.

¹ The graphic reconstructions presented in this article were created with the assistance of ChatGPT (OpenAI). In addition, the Gemini artificial intelligence system (Google)

Figure 2. Graphic reconstruction of an element of the ritual of sewing shut a frog's mouth inside a dwelling.

From these descriptions, several characteristic features of the ritual may be identified:

- The primary purpose of the ritual was to influence social hierarchies and relations of authority.
- The sounds produced by the frog appear to have been considered significant. Although the sources do not explain their meaning, they may have been interpreted as a form of divination concerning the actions of the authorities symbolically represented by the frog whose mouth had been sewn shut.
- The type of thread used in the ritual was clearly important, although the colour was not fixed and could vary.
- The time of day played a role, as frogs were to be captured at dawn.
- The sources do not specify what was to be done with the frog after the ritual. This omission may indicate that the animal's subsequent fate was not regarded as an essential element of the practice.

Since actions of this kind were subject to legal prosecution in the Hetmanate, other regions of Ukraine, and the Russian Empire, it is unlikely that more explicit explanations of such rituals by the practitioners themselves have survived. In order to gain a better understanding of this magical tradition, it is therefore necessary to undertake a comparative analysis with cultures in which similar practices have been documented, particularly where they have remained in use until recent times.

It is equally important to identify magical traditions in which such rituals have not been recorded, as this may help clarify the cultural and symbolic differences between distinct systems of belief and practice.

Let us begin with traditions in which the sewing shut of a frog's mouth is still practised today. Such examples can be found in Brazil, elsewhere in Latin America, and throughout the Caribbean.

Particular attention should be paid to the Brazilian syncretic religious traditions associated with magical practices involving frogs, commonly known as *Trabalho de Sapo* (4). Of special interest here are binding rituals in which the act of "closing the mouth" is intended to restrict or control the agency of a person symbolically identified with the frog. The underlying symbolism has been preserved, although the technical details vary; for example, wire may be used instead of thread.

Such rituals are sufficiently widespread that law-enforcement authorities have occasionally attempted to suppress them. Official interventions are directed not against alleged magical practices as such, but rather against acts considered to constitute cruelty to animals.

Figure 3. A frog with its mouth sealed with wire in a Brazilian binding-magic ritual

In Latin America and the Caribbean, contemporary examples of this practice are rarely discussed in academic literature. However, comparable cases occasionally appear in newspaper reports and police chronicles (5).

One such example was reported in Peru in 2014. A frog with its mouth sewn shut was discovered buried in a small box near a grave in a cemetery. Residents of the city of Cajamarca who encountered the object while visiting the cemetery interpreted it as evidence of a magical ritual. According to local media reports, they believed that the ritual may have been intended to influence a particular family. Concerned by the discovery, they reported the matter to the police, which subsequently attracted media attention.

Several details are noteworthy. As in the Ukrainian cases, black thread was used. Another significant feature is the placement of the frog within a container situated near human burials. This suggests a possible connection between the ritual object and the deceased individual or the social group associated with the burial, although the precise purpose of the ritual remains uncertain.

Figure 4. A frog with its mouth sewn shut, discovered in Peru

In the Caribbean, a similar case was reported in 2014 in Castries, the capital of the island nation of Saint Lucia. A live frog with its mouth sewn shut was discovered inside a courthouse (6). The animal was subsequently removed from the building and covered with salt, which, according to local folk beliefs, was thought to neutralize the effects of the alleged magical act.

Individuals who were scheduled to testify that day later claimed that they had remained unable to speak because of the ritual. As a result, the court hearing could not proceed as planned.

This case represents a particularly clear example of what may be described as judicial magic. It is also noteworthy for the attempt to counteract the ritual's presumed effects through the use of salt, a substance widely associated with ritual purification and protection in many folk traditions.

Figure 5. A frog with its mouth sewn shut found near a courthouse in the Caribbean

Let us now turn to Western Europe, a cultural region in which this tradition appears to have largely disappeared but nevertheless left a significant cultural legacy (7). Because European cultural models exerted a profound influence on global perceptions of magic for several centuries, it is primarily within this tradition that contemporary popular images of witchcraft have been formed.

As a result, many of the concepts, symbols, and practices now commonly associated with witchcraft can be traced to the historical magical beliefs and traditions of Western Europe.

Figure 6. A frog with its mouth sewn shut: an exhibit in a French museum (7)

Within the context of Western magical traditions, which have been among the most extensively theorized and documented forms of folk belief, numerous sources describe practices commonly classified as sympathetic magic. Such practices are based upon a mythological mode of perception in which actions performed upon a symbolic substitute are believed to affect the intended target.

The notion of a symbolic substitute should be understood broadly. In the cases examined here, this role is fulfilled by the frog, an animal whose body may be perceived as

roughly analogous to that of a human being, possessing a head, limbs, and torso, but distinguished by the prominence of its mouth. Ritual actions directed at this feature are intended to affect a person symbolically associated with the animal, for example by restricting that individual's ability to speak effectively in a legal setting.

Because the principle of sympathetic resemblance is characteristic of many magical traditions, the initial assumption of this study was that rituals involving the sewing shut of a frog's mouth would be widely distributed wherever frogs were readily available as ritual instruments.

The evidence, however, has produced a more complex picture. The ritual appears to be documented primarily in a limited number of regions and associated belief systems: Eastern and Western Europe, parts of Latin America (particularly the Brazil–Peru area), and the Caribbean.

By contrast, the author has not identified reliable evidence for comparable practices in Haitian Vodou, African American Hoodoo, Russian folk magical traditions, or the African materials consulted for this study.

The case of Hoodoo deserves particular attention. This syncretic magical tradition emerged among enslaved populations in the southern United States and incorporated elements derived from the religious and cultural traditions of their regions of origin. At the same time, Hoodoo became deeply integrated into the broader social environment of the United States while retaining distinctive ethnographic characteristics. As a result, researchers in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries were able to document many aspects of the living tradition in considerable detail.

Consequently, a substantial body of reliable scholarship exists that reflects vernacular magical beliefs and practices in a cultural setting where trained observers were able to record them systematically. Examination of one of the major studies devoted to the subject (9) reveals that, despite numerous ritual uses of frogs—including beating them, cutting them open, sewing objects into them, drying them, and employing them in various other magical operations—no ritual analogous to the sewing shut of a frog's mouth has been identified.

Instead, similar objectives were often pursued through other ritual means. For example, Hoodoo practitioners frequently employed the tongue of cattle, which could be purchased as food but was subsequently used in magical operations involving nails, pins, and other forms of symbolic manipulation intended to affect speech.

The reasons for the selective geographical distribution of the frog-mouth-sewing ritual remain unclear. Its occurrence cannot be explained simply by the availability of amphibians.

One possible hypothesis is that the ritual may correlate with deeper Christian or pre-Christian patterns of belief.

According to this interpretation, where a frog's mouth is sewn shut, the animal functions primarily as a symbolic representation of the intended target—the person whose speech or agency is to be restricted. In other traditions characterized by animistic conceptions of a spirit-filled world, however, the frog may be understood less as a representation of a person than as a vessel containing a supernatural force, making access to the animal's interior symbolically significant.

At present, however, this hypothesis remains speculative. Since no reliable evidence for the ritual has yet been identified in Russian materials (10), despite the historical prominence of Orthodox Christianity in that region, the proposed explanation cannot be regarded as sufficiently substantiated.

In previous research, votive practices within Slavic countries were shown to possess many common features (11). In the present case, however, a clear divergence appears to exist. Future archival and ethnographic discoveries may nevertheless reveal evidence of comparable traditions in regions where they have not yet been documented.

The evidence presented above allows the following conclusions to be drawn:

- The ritual of sewing shut a frog's mouth formed part of the Ukrainian folk magical tradition. Within popular belief, it appears to have been regarded as a taboo practice and employed only in situations perceived as requiring exceptional measures.
- Comparable rituals are documented in several cultural traditions as a form of sympathetic or binding magic, including cases that may be interpreted as examples of judicial magic. In this context, the ritual descriptions preserved in the Ukrainian archival materials appear plausible and consistent with broader comparative evidence.
- The ritual cannot be regarded as a universal feature of magical traditions. Its geographical and cultural distribution appears to have been selective. The reasons for this pattern remain unclear, although it is possible that differences in the penetration of Christian beliefs into local folk cultures played a role in shaping the ritual's development and transmission.

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